

Received 20 February 2025, accepted 25 March 2025, date of publication 15 April 2025, date of current version 5 May 2025.

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3561220

RESEARCH ARTICLE

From Reports to Actions: Bridging the Customer Usability Gap in Penetration Testing

KATARINA GALANSKA¹, AGATA KRUIKOVA¹, MARIA PIBILOTA MURUMAA²,
VÁCLAV MATYÁŠ¹, AND MIKE JUST³

¹Masaryk University, 601 77 Brno, Czech Republic

²Cybernetica AS, 12618 Tallinn, Estonia

³Heriot-Watt University, EH14 4AS Edinburgh, U.K.

Corresponding author: Katarina Galanska (galanska@mail.muni.cz)

This work involved human subjects or animals in its research. The authors confirm that all human/animal subject research procedures and protocols are exempt from review board approval.

ABSTRACT Penetration testing reports play a significant role in helping organizations identify and mitigate security vulnerabilities. The report effectiveness relies on the extent to which customers can translate the findings into actionable decisions. Our study investigates usability gaps in penetration testing reports from a customer-centric perspective, focusing on the challenges organizations face in understanding, prioritizing, and acting on the provided insights. Within the study, we demonstrated a penetration testing scenario together to IT professionals scaled from technical to managerial. We provided them with a selected reported vulnerability finding from the scenario. By conducting surveys and focus groups, we aimed to identify common gaps. Based on data from 25 focus group participants, we conducted a thematic analysis, identifying 8 themes with 29 findings categorized as possible improvements, gaps, and general perceptions, highlighting weaknesses in PT reports. The results highlight the necessity of aligning report content with the needs of specific target audiences. Key findings reveal gaps in defining the scope, rules of engagement, and methodology before conducting PT, as well as inadequacies in describing findings within reports. Additionally, our research underscores the importance of incorporating positive findings and enhancing security recommendations by avoiding generic mitigations, providing multiple mitigation options, assessing their impact, and specifying preferred solutions when applicable. The study explores how these gaps can affect decision-making processes, risk mitigation efforts, and overall cybersecurity outcomes. By highlighting these issues, our research sheds light on the need for improved usability in penetration testing deliverables to better serve customer needs and enhance cybersecurity outcomes.

INDEX TERMS Penetration testing, security advice, security report, usability.

I. INTRODUCTION

Penetration testing (PT) reports, as the only tangible product of PT, are significant in ensuring that effective cybersecurity measures are implemented within an organization [1], [2]. The test itself often takes several days to complete, and the report should contain a description of the work done. This report provides detailed information on potential vulnerabilities identified during testing, enabling key stakeholders,

including IT managers, technical staff, and senior executives, to make informed decisions on risk mitigation and resource allocation.

A penetration test is a technique used to assess the security of an IT system by attempting to exploit its vulnerabilities, employing the same tools and methods that a potential attacker would use. The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) defines PT as follows:

A method of testing in which testers target individual binary components or the applica-

The associate editor coordinating the review of this manuscript and approving it for publication was Tyson Brooks¹.

tion as a whole to determine whether intra- or intercomponent vulnerabilities can be exploited to compromise the application, its data, or its environment resources [3].

PT reports not only outline the weaknesses of tested systems, but also provide the reader with security advice on each finding. The approach of reporting security vulnerabilities impacts the accuracy and time required to patch them [4]. Therefore, it is important to write the report recommendations in a “usable way” (e.g., clear, unambiguous) to prevent possible misunderstandings leading to incorrect remediations or mitigation delays. If the recommendation is not delivered correctly, developers might choose ineffective solutions to the vulnerability. For example, developers who find solutions to programming problems online on public platforms often tend to choose an insecure solution [5].

To identify specific challenges in the usability of security advice in PT, we set two research questions to guide our research:

RQ1 What are the perceptions of IT professionals about PT reports?

RQ2 Where are the shortcomings in PT reports from the usability perspective of an IT professional?

In order to understand the problems, we conducted three user workshop studies with the consumers of PT reports. The first study was conducted as part of a larger conference, where we demonstrated to participants the scenario of a PT from the tester’s perspective. We provided them with a specific finding that describes one of the vulnerabilities exploited within the demonstration. We collected participants’ feedback in the form of a survey questionnaire in which we asked if what they see is what they would expect to see in the report as a customer. Selected questions were targeting their overall perceptions of penetration testing reports. We extended the following studies by adding focus groups with predefined structure as individual parts of our workshops. Those two studies were conducted as standalone events.

Having results from 25 focus groups participants, we performed a thematic analysis of the data collected and identified eight themes: PT finding, recommendation, crucial parts, approach to PT, customization, advanced challenges, target groups, and positive talk. Within the themes, we identified 29 findings. The findings are categorized into the following groups: gaps in the current usability of the reports, potential improvements to bridge these gaps, and insights from the consumers of the reports. In general, our results provide an overview of the weak points in the PT reports.

We contribute to the improvement of penetration testing usability by providing a deeper insight into a topic where limited research has been done so far. By exploring how consumers of PT reports interpret the reports, this study sheds light on the challenges and barriers faced in understanding complex security information. We contribute by identifying user perceptions and key areas where improvements could be made, such as descriptions of findings, given recommendations, customization of PT reports, positive talk, problems with different target groups, and advanced challenges.

The paper is structured into the following sections. Section II provides an overview of PT research from the perspective of usability, standardization, usable security principles, current research on security advice, and currently identified gaps in research in this area. Section III explains the methodology of our study, and Section IV presents the data analysis and results. In Section V we then present our perception and adoption of results and discuss how these results address our research questions. Section VI concludes the findings and proposes possible future work.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section provides relevant background on the usability of penetration testing reports. Unlike fields with established standards, penetration testing methods vary widely among professionals and organizations, leading to inconsistencies, limited comparability in evaluations, and overlooked security weaknesses.

Previous research analyzed eight PT reports from various sources to examine the consistency and commonalities of their structures and contents [6]. They highlight differences and similarities in the way these reports present essential data. From this analysis, it became apparent that there is no standard format for presenting penetration test findings, indicating room for improvement in facilitating comprehension and actionability for IT professionals. Based on their analysis, they recommend the following components to be a part of the report: executive summary, scope of work, project objectives, timeline, summary of findings, and summary of recommendations.

While considerable research has been focused on improving the effectiveness of various aspects of cybersecurity practices (e.g., [7], [8], [9]), the usability of PT reports has received relatively less attention [4]. Research related to usable security of cryptographic resources like standards and libraries shows that usability tends to take a secondary position, resulting in complicated solutions that hinder developers from making smart security choices [9]. In general, these developments illustrate the increasing recognition of the critical role that usability plays in improving security guidelines.

When discussing security advice given to IT professionals, recent and relevant research has focused mainly on the advice provided by static analysis tools [10], [11], [12]. In one study [13], developers were given the security advice produced by static analysis tools and their questions about the tools’ recommendations were analysed. Many of the questions asked were related to understanding the vulnerabilities themselves and the suggested mitigations. Additionally, the developers asked about location of information or connections of multiple vulnerabilities.

One study of security guides for developers found that they often lack updated content and detailed step-by-step instructions, including practical code snippets or hands-on exercises [14]. While many target different skill levels and are easily searchable, there remains room for improvement in providing more thorough and user-friendly secure program-

TABLE 1. Number of participants.

Workshop Location	Survey	Focus Group	# of Groups
Prague, CZ	29	0	0
Tallinn, EE	17	11	1
Tartu, EE	15	14	2
Total	61	25	3

ming guidance. Unlike other previously mentioned research, this study focused on general sources of security guidelines designed to help developers while excluding forum posts and Q&A platforms.

A recent study has introduced a deep learning-based approach to not only find vulnerabilities, but also describe them [15]. In their research, they acknowledge that improving the quality of the generated descriptions is not trivial.

With respect to vulnerabilities, it has been shown that the main source of vulnerabilities in cryptographic software is related to incorrect usage rather than bugs in the cryptographic libraries themselves [16]. This also emphasizes the importance of usability in penetration test reports—if a vulnerability is caused by incorrect usage or integration, simply identifying it without providing a clear explanation of the fix may not be effective.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the research design, data collection methods, and analytical techniques employed to investigate the gaps in the PT reports.

We conducted three studies with cybersecurity professionals from several companies that work with PT reports. The studies were carried out during three separate workshop events. Our target group consisted of cybersecurity specialists, defined as individuals who work in cybersecurity roles at companies that are customers of companies, which provide PT as a service. Participants were invited to participate through partner companies, AEC a.s. in Czechia (CZ) and Cybernetica AS in Estonia (EE). More than 50 participants attended the workshop in Czechia and 32 participants in Estonia.

A. STUDY PROCEDURE

A workshop involved the following planned steps:

- 1) A demonstration of PT scenario
- 2) A survey participation (questionnaire)
- 3) A focus group

The first study was conducted in Czechia (Prague) as part of a larger conference. The conference was organized by AEC a.s., a company providing PT as a service. Participants could voluntarily register for our workshop based on the invitation poster provided. The goal of the workshop was to demonstrate to the participants what they normally do not see, a scenario of how a penetration tester works. It was followed by a quantitative survey that asked two types of questions. As part of the survey, we aimed to show the participants what the report of such a penetration test would look like and ask them if this is what they

would expect. In addition, certain questions were dedicated to collecting general perceptions of these reports with which participants have already worked. Overall, the first workshop consisted of a demonstration of a PT scenario, including a demonstration of a finding connected to the exploitation demonstrated as a first step. Participants received a two-page description of the vulnerability exploited during the demonstration, together with a two-page classification description of severity, remediation effort, and probability.

After running the first study, we decided to extend the study by adding focus groups in order to collect more detailed insights.

The following two studies were conducted in Estonia (in two days in two different cities, Tallinn and Tartu). The workshops have been organized as standalone events. Together, three separate focus groups were conducted in Estonia. The focus groups were designed to have a specific predefined structure. Therefore, the same topics were discussed in each focus group, but each time with different participants. The purpose of the study was to identify gaps in PT reports. Data from the first study were collected on the 24th May 2023, and data from the following studies were collected on the 2nd and 3rd November 2023. The numbers of participants are provided in Table 1.

The workshop took approximately an hour to complete, the survey took approximately 15 minutes to complete, and each focus group lasted about an hour.

1) DEMONSTRATION

The demonstration consisted of a small number of slides to introduce the topic of PT and a presentation of a PT scenario. During the demonstration, the focus was on what lies behind the PT report, providing all participants with the same baseline for further discussion and evaluation. The scenario included exploitations of five vulnerabilities taken from a real PT report performed by a PT company. The vulnerabilities were implemented in the web application created for demonstration purposes. The scenario demonstration did not follow a full PT methodology, but included parts of reconnaissance, exploration, and exploitation guided by the presenter. For each vulnerability in the scenario, the presenter showed a step-by-step approach to identify a specific finding the same way it would be performed by the penetration tester. The difference was that the presenter did not try to test each endpoint and request, as only relevant vulnerable endpoints were selected for the demonstration purpose.

The goal was to show participants how a specific penetration test scenario is conducted, enabling them to assess the content of the vulnerability finding in the report and identify what they would like to see included. Five vulnerabilities were presented, along with demonstrations of their exploitation: information leakage from *robots.txt* file, enabled debug mode with stack trace information leakage, possible session hijacking, XXE external entity injection, and template injection with remote code execution.

The workshop was designed for people working with PT reports from a customer's perspective, including both people

working in technical and in managerial roles. In addition, all participants were required to have a professional experience in cybersecurity. The diversity of technical to managerial participants allowed for a broad range of perspectives on the usability of the security documentation, as PT reports also have multiple target groups.

2) SURVEY

Following the demonstration, participants received a description of a selected finding chosen from the five vulnerabilities demonstrated and exploited, along with a survey. In our case a finding is a description of one specific vulnerability together with a description of where it was found, a description of the risk, severity, probability, remediation effort, and a recommendation for mitigation of the vulnerability. The survey aimed to collect general perceptions of the PT reports and those parts of report, the participants worked with and included specific questions about the description of the finding provided.

The survey was structured into three sections. The first aimed to collect demographic data. The participants self-assessed their level of experience, how many PT reports they had worked with, and whether their role was more technical or managerial in nature.

The second section of the survey aimed to gather more general perceptions and overall opinions about PT reports. This part included questions about the importance of various parts of the description of the finding.

The last section of the survey was directly related to the earlier demonstration. The question continued with asking if the given *XXE External Entity Injection* finding in the report includes all the necessary information to address the vulnerabilities. Participants received the description of *XXE External Entity Injection* finding, demonstrated and exploited within the demonstration, and were further asked about the quality of the specific parts of the finding and the general satisfaction with the description of the finding. The survey included two open questions: one asking if the findings were clearly understood and another inviting participants to suggest improvements on how the findings could be communicated more effectively.

3) FOCUS GROUP STRUCTURE

The first study collected data solely through a survey, but some participants expressed a desire to discuss the topic in more depth. These insights encouraged us to collect some qualitative feedback from workshop participants in the future. Therefore, we decided to add focus groups as part of the two future workshops in Estonia. The results of the first study and the analysis of the survey highlighted that the report needs to evolve to better meet the diverse needs of stakeholders in the cybersecurity landscape. The identified areas of the first study were used as the basis for the structure of the focus groups.

The focus group(s) followed the demonstration and the survey after a short break, giving participants who did not wish to continue and participate in the focus group a chance to leave. The same participants responded to a

quantitative survey and then continued with a focus group in each workshop. After explaining the data collection process and obtaining verbal consent for the audio recording, the participants were divided into focus groups of about 8 participants each. Each focus group was held in a separate room and a dedicated moderator posed questions to the group and encouraged responses from all participants in each group. The group discussed their response to the question. Each focus group followed the same predefined structure of questions.

The focus group included the following sections:

- 1) **Roles and responsibilities:** Each participant was asked to clarify their role and primary responsibilities within the company, particularly in relation to the PT reports. They were also asked to share their motivation for joining the focus group. This question served two purposes: first, as an opening warm-up to help participants feel more comfortable, and second, to determine whether our participants approached the topic from a managerial or technical perspective.
- 2) **Key expectations from a PT report:** Participants were asked about their key expectations from a penetration test and how well the resulting report typically meets those expectations in terms of understanding the test details. They were encouraged to provide examples, identify specific challenges, and suggest possible areas for improvement.
- 3) **Crucial elements in addressing vulnerabilities:** After identifying what areas the participants perceived as important, we shifted their attention to the most critical parts of PT reports to deal with security issues within their organization. They were encouraged to provide examples of particularly valuable elements and explain the impact of these elements on the subsequent steps taken by their organization to implement security measures based on the findings of the report.
- 4) **Approach to addressing vulnerabilities:** We then delved deeper, asking participants to describe the typical steps their organization takes when addressing vulnerabilities identified in PT reports, including how the responsibilities are distributed among team members or departments.
- 5) **Customization and alignment:** This section focused on how reports could be tailored or adapted to better align with the unique security goals and needs of their organizations. Participants were also asked to provide examples, possibly addressing differences between the recommended actions and those actually performed.
- 6) **Level of detail:** We then explored the perceptions of the participants about the level of detail in the security advice provided within the PT reports. They were encouraged to give examples where the details were helpful or lacking, as well as situations where too much or too little detail was provided.
- 7) **One or more suggested solutions:** Participants were asked for their opinions on PT reports that provide only one solution to a security issue. They were encouraged

to give examples where a single solution provided was effective or limiting and to discuss the impact of having provided multiple solution options.

- 8) **Highlighted improvement:** In this exit question, which helped close the focus group, participants were asked to mention one major improvement that they wanted to highlight from the focus group discussion.

After the focus group, there was time for the participants to freely approach the interviewing team with any questions or to share additional comments.

B. DATA ANALYSIS

Since this is an introductory research into the topic, quantitative survey data are reported as descriptors to enrich our results from focus groups. Data collection was done solely in the English language.

In order to analyze the data, the recordings were first transcribed using a simple Python script using an offline speech-to-text engine. Secondly, the transcribed text was manually edited by the researchers in order to prevent errors from automatic transcription.

Qualitative data obtained through focus groups were analyzed using thematic analysis methods [17]. The following procedure was applied:

- Familiarizing with the data: This included the transcription of audio data.
- Inductive coding: The creation of initial codes was done by the first author. A codebook was created and subsequently reviewed by another author. In case of disagreement, it was discussed until an agreement was reached. Since we used this approach, the reliability between the authors was not computed [18], [19].
- Themes: Identifying themes and then reviewing them to establish the final themes was done by the first author.

C. ETHICS

Participation in our study was purely voluntary. Participants could opt out at any time. The first round of the study consisted solely of the survey, ensuring anonymity. The second and third round included both survey and audio recordings. These audio recordings were accessed and manually transcribed exclusively by the first author of this paper and deleted after transcription. Identifiable information mentioned during focus groups was removed from the transcripts. Participants were not asked for any identifiable information, such as the company they represent. Participants were informed of and consented to the audio recording and the described processing procedures both verbally and by receiving the written notice. While participants were not compensated, they were provided with refreshments during the event.

IV. RESULTS

This section presents the key findings of the study and offers a detailed analysis of the data collected. The identified findings were categorized into three distinct groups: gaps, insights, and improvements, illustrated in Table 2. The categorization

TABLE 2. Legend of results categories and symbols.

Category	Description	Symbol
Insights	Views or beliefs held by participants regarding the subject.	💡
Gaps	Areas where deficiencies or missing elements were identified.	🔍
Improvements	Suggested changes or enhancements based on the findings.	🔧

provides a structured approach to analyze the findings and provides information on the different dimensions of the problem.

The categories are distinguished throughout the article by specific icons, allowing for easy identification and reference to each group in the analysis.

Each finding is further represented by another symbol that indicates the number of focus groups in which it was discussed. There are three possible icons: If the finding was discussed in only one focus group, it is marked with 👤. If it was discussed in two focus groups, the finding is marked with 👥. Finally, if the finding was discussed in all focus groups, it will be marked with 👨‍👩‍👦.

The subsections below present results regarding the participant sample, survey results and focus group results. Each subsection provides a detailed analysis of the findings specific to these data collection methods. The Focus Groups Results subsection is further divided with respect to identified themes explored during the study.

A. SAMPLE

We collected together 61 survey responses, as shown in Table 1. The survey gathered responses from individuals with varying experience levels, roles, and exposure to PT reports. The respondents had a wide range of experience in cybersecurity.

In the first workshop conducted in Prague, 29 participants took part in the survey. The next two workshops in Estonia additionally added 17 and 15 filled surveys and recordings from the focus groups.

The participants held diverse roles within their organizations. A significant proportion (35%) had managerial roles, 30% had mixed roles, and 35% had technical roles. The survey revealed that 45% of the respondents had worked with fewer than 5 PT reports, 18% had worked with between 5 and 10 reports, 10% had worked with between 11 and 15 reports and 27% had reviewed more than 10 reports.

Additionally, data was collected from three focus groups. The focus groups included a total of 25 participants, with representation from technical to managerial cybersecurity positions. The sample for the focus groups was a subset of the sample for the survey. In the first workshop, the representation of managerial and technical roles was balanced. In the third workshop, there were two-thirds more

technical roles. The roles ranged from developers, system administrators, and testers to project managers, heads of security, and security officers.

B. SURVEY RESULTS

1) GAPS

The survey revealed several key insights into current practices and user preferences. A significant number (38%) rated security advice in PT reports as inadequate, poor, or very poor with respect to usability. Fewer participants rated the description of the remediation effort and severity as poor or very poor quality, while none of the participants rated the description of the finding (how the vulnerability has been found) as poor.

Interestingly, 40% of the participants expressed dissatisfaction with the current level of detail of most reports that describe the vulnerabilities within the report.

2) IMPROVEMENTS

Participants who expressed dissatisfaction with the current level of detail in the description of the findings indicated a preference for more comprehensive explanations of the vulnerabilities identified and their potential impact on the organization. This aligns with the finding that 10% of the participants favored reports that include references to best practices to help them understand complex information more effectively.

A number of participants (10%) wanted more options to mitigate the reported vulnerability. User feedback also underscored the importance of providing vulnerability descriptions for non-technical people, with 8% of the respondents preferring step-by-step explanations.

Furthermore, two participants expressed that they would prefer the integration of information that identifies the level of expertise of the person required to work on the mitigation.

Overall, the results of the survey suggest a strong demand for clear, actionable and more detailed PT reports.

C. FOCUS GROUPS RESULTS

Through thematic analysis, several key themes emerged from the focus group discussions. These themes highlight the main usability issues, user experiences with the security documentation, and their suggestions for improvement.

1) CRUCIAL PARTS

One of the initial questions of the focus groups was aimed at crucial parts of the PT reports. Our analysis indicated some differences between the views of technical and managerial participants.

What is crucial for managers: For cybersecurity managers, as illustrated in Fig. 1, it is important to receive clear and concise executive summaries, detailed yet accessible explanations of vulnerabilities, actionable recommendations and definitions of methodology and scope. The executive summary was shown to be particularly important for decision makers who claim to not have the time or technical expertise to delve into

the entire report. The summary provides them with a snapshot of the most critical findings and their potential impact.

FIGURE 1. Managerial Perspective of Crucial Part of PT Report.

What is crucial for technicians: On the other hand, from the technician’s perspective, as shown in Fig. 2, detailed step-by-step explanations of how the vulnerabilities have been found and how to fix them are necessary to fully understand the nature of the vulnerabilities identified and their possible mitigations. Lastly, actionable recommendations were shown to be essential for translating the findings into practical steps that the organization can take to mitigate risks, ensuring that the report leads to tangible security improvements.

FIGURE 2. Technician perspective of crucial part of PT report.

2) APPROACH TO PT

A significant theme that emerged from the analysis revolves around the problems caused by a poorly defined approach to PT, particularly concerning the rules of engagement, scope definition, and following a methodology while performing the penetration test.

- Rules of engagement:** Respondents in each focus group highlighted issues arising when the scope of the test is not properly defined, leading to incomplete or irrelevant findings that do not accurately reflect the organization’s security posture.
- Scope definition:** The feedback underscores the importance of clearly defined, mutually agreed-upon parameters and objectives before testing begins to ensure that the report is both comprehensive and aligned with the organization’s security goals.
- Methodology definition:** Lastly, but very importantly, the frequently discussed topic was the PT methodology. The majority of participants agreed that a

PT methodology is often not clearly defined. It can lead to significant issues that undermine the effectiveness of the entire testing process.

3) PT FINDING

The following insights, gaps and improvements, as shown in Fig. 3 are related to the finding part of the PT report.

FIGURE 3. Theme of PT finding.

- 💡 **Positive findings:** Another suggested improvement is to write positive findings alongside identified vulnerabilities. By highlighting areas where security measures are functioning correctly, reports can provide a balanced view that not only identifies vulnerabilities, but also acknowledges strengths.
- 🔗 **Unusable CVSS scoring:** Participants have indicated that CVSS scoring can be unusable, particularly for non-technical stakeholders, due to its complexity and lack of context. Although CVSS provides a standardized method for assessing the severity of vulnerabilities, it often fails to capture the business impact or prioritize issues in a way that aligns with the organization's specific risk profile, making it less effective for guiding actionable decisions.
- 🔗 **Proof of concept:** Describing a finding in the context of how a vulnerability was perceived as crucial for providing a clear and actionable PT report. This aspect of the finding involves detailing the specific techniques, tools, steps the tester used to identify the vulnerability, and even the level of expertise of the penetration tester.
- 🔗 **Reproducibility:** Participants mentioned that they would expect to read about the reconnaissance methods that revealed a misconfigured server, the use of particular scanning tools that detected outdated software, or the manual testing procedures that revealed an insecure authentication mechanism. By explaining how the vulnerability was found, the readers could validate

the pathways that an attacker could take to exploit the vulnerability.

- 🔗 **Additional resources:** Including additional resources was shown to be essential to replicate the testing process, allowing the organization to verify the vulnerability and better understand its root cause.
- 🔗 **CVSS scoring as plus:** An improvement discussed is to provide clear classification of findings, for example, using Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) metrics.

4) RECOMMENDATION

Another set of study findings relates to the recommendation part of the PT report. The set of gaps and improvements are illustrated in Fig. 4.

FIGURE 4. Theme of recommendation.

- 🔗 **Recommendation for non-technical people:** Using straightforward language, well-organized sections, and consistent terminology could, based on user feedback, make reports more accessible to both technical and non-technical stakeholders.
- 🔗 **Mitigation impact:** Participants also emphasized the importance of including the mitigation impact in PT reports. In addition to multiple mitigation options and a preferred solution, they want a clear explanation of how each mitigation would affect the system, security posture, and business operations.
- 🔗 **Multiple mitigations:** Participants have expressed the need for multiple mitigation options in PT reports, rather than a single solution. Providing a variety of mitigation strategies would allow organizations to choose an approach that best fits their resources, risk tolerance, and operational constraints. This flexibility would ensure that remediation efforts are both effective and practical, accommodating different technical environments and business priorities.

- ✂ **Copy-pasted recommendation:** Participants have expressed frustration with copy-pasted mitigations in PT reports, meaning when a penetration tester uses the same recommendation for the same generic type of vulnerabilities in multiple reports without customizing it. These generic solutions often do not consider the unique context of their specific environments.
- ✂ **Step by step example:** Another prominent theme was the insufficiency of actionable recommendations in the reports. Many respondents expressed frustration that, while reports identify vulnerabilities, they often do not provide concrete, step-by-step guidance on addressing these issues.
- ✂ **Preferred mitigation:** In addition to multiple mitigation options, participants have indicated a preference to have a preferred mitigation clearly highlighted in PT reports. This approach would allow decision-makers to balance between ideal and practical mitigation strategies.

This lack of actionable advice makes it challenging for organizations to prioritize and implement the necessary changes to improve their security posture. The respondents highlighted the need for the reports to include specific practical recommendations that align with the resources and capabilities of the organization, ensuring that the findings lead to meaningful improvements.

5) CUSTOMIZATION

The study resulted in three insights, presented in Fig. 5, related to the customization of the PT report.

FIGURE 5. Theme of customization.

- 💡 **Company size-dependent security advice:** Different sized companies require differently tailored PT reports, as smaller businesses need concise, high-priority recommendations, while larger organizations require more detailed, comprehensive reports that address complex infrastructures and compliance requirements.
- 💡 **Machine readability:** Participants need the penetration test reports to be machine readable to automate responses and for continuous improvement in security measures by adapting the findings of previous tests to evolving threats.
- 💡 **Comparison to average security posture:** The participants, mainly managerial oriented, declared the

need to compare the security posture of the company tested, based on penetration test reports to assess their progress over time, benchmark against industry standards, and identify gaps in their defenses to prioritize future improvements.

6) POSITIVE TALK

Two insights, shown in Fig. 6, relate to participants' positive perceptions of PT report.

FIGURE 6. Theme of positive talk.

- 💡 **Penetration tester helps with the first step:** Respondents emphasized that PT report as such is very helpful for minimizing vulnerabilities found, even when the recommendation for vulnerabilities found might be generic, it serves as guidance for initial remediation steps.
- 💡 **Confidence from concrete evidence:** In one focus group, respondents agreed that the report itself, when written correctly, serves as concrete evidence for the current state of security of the application tested.

7) TARGET GROUPS

The theme addresses different target groups of the PT report. The following two findings, shown in Fig. 7, represents one insight and one possible improvement.

FIGURE 7. Theme of target groups.

- ✂ **Labels:** Another discussed topic with respect to different target groups of the report is tailoring the recommendation section and labeling it for specific audiences. For example, high-level strategic recommendations could be marked for management, while technical steps for mitigation would be directed at IT staff, ensuring that everyone understands their role in addressing the issue without the need for separate reports.
- 💡 **Multiple levels of report:** PT report serves multiple target groups. This fact was discussed within all focus groups that were conducted. Participants highlighted the

need for every reader, managerial or technical, to understand the security issues, their impact, and remediation and highlighted the potential benefit of tailoring the content of findings to different levels of the target audience. For high management, a summary report would focus on overall risk and strategic recommendations, while a more detailed report for technicians would include specific findings, technical vulnerabilities, and remediation steps for implementation.

8) ADVANCED CHALLENGES

The theme of advanced challenges in PT reports, shown in Fig. 8, addresses several critical issues that have been merged into the theme, which represents improvements that could be done to PT as such, but are more difficult to address compared to adding labels to the report template.

FIGURE 8. Theme of advanced challenges.

- 💡 👤 **Unclear PT regulations:** One major challenge discussed in each focus group is the presence of unclear or evolving regulations, which makes it difficult for organizations to understand compliance requirements and for testers to align their methodologies with legal expectations. This lack of standards and regulations defining how exactly the penetration test should be performed, based on the discussions, leads to inconsistent testing results and the feeling of uncertainty about the adequacy of security measures.
- 💡 👤 **Methodology consistency:** Another challenge is ensuring consistency in the testing methodology, as different testers may approach the same environment with varying techniques and focus areas, leading to discrepancies in findings and recommendations.
- 💡 👤 **Penetration tester fix knowledge:** The depth of the penetration tester's knowledge plays a crucial role in the quality of the report. A tester with limited experience or understanding of specific technologies may overlook critical vulnerabilities or fail to provide actionable advice, thereby compromising the effectiveness of the test.
- 💡 👤 **Norm comparison to others:** Managerial participants prefer PT reports to include industry comparisons,

offering a benchmark for their organization's security posture. For example, they value insights like "Your security in this domain is better than the industry average", which provides context and helps assess how their defenses stack up against competitors. This kind of comparison would allow them to make informed decisions on where to focus resources and improvements in relation to industry standards.

- 💡 👤 **Compliance of different assessment methods:** Standards are established that define assessment methods, such as those used in risk management, which typically involve identifying, evaluating and prioritizing risks based on impact and likelihood. These methods differ from the way the results of the penetration tests are provided, as PT focuses on identifying specific vulnerabilities through simulated attacks and providing detailed technical findings. The focus groups showed that this non-compliance of different assessment methods presents a gap in regular security activities within companies.

The findings of the focus group reveal significant usability issues in current security documentation, including problems with clarity, relevance, and security guidance. The results also bring new ideas for improvement and the insights of other participants. Addressing these issues can improve the overall usability and effectiveness of the documentation, making it more accessible and helpful for users. In the next chapter, we discuss these findings in the context of the existing literature and propose recommendations to improve the usability of security documentation based on the insights gathered from the results.

V. DISCUSSIONS

This chapter draws connections between the findings and the core research objectives, offering insights into how the data answers the key questions posed in the study. Through a detailed examination of the results, the chapter aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the implications and relevance of our research. The structure of the chapter follows the same structure of themes as the results (Section IV), which discusses and highlights critical findings within the results. The discussion will incorporate quotes from participants to enrich the analysis and provide deeper insights into their perspectives.

A. CRUCIAL PARTS

Participants' views on the crucial parts of the penetration testing reports are consistent with the results reported by previous researchers, who also examined the structure of the penetration testing reports by analyzing eight different examples [6].

The results revealed distinct priorities between technicians and managers regarding the crucial aspects identified in the study.

"Now I feel that PT report should contain some specific parts not only for the technical people but

also for the business side because they are giving the money to fix all the problems.”

The differences underscore the importance of tailoring communication and interventions to the specific needs and roles of each group, ensuring that both technical and managerial priorities are adequately addressed.

B. APPROACH TO PT

Under the theme *approach to PT*, three specific gaps were mentioned consistently across all focus groups: rules of engagement, scope definition, and methodology definition. This widespread recognition highlights the importance and relevance of these findings, indicating that they represent key concerns or perspectives shared by participants regardless of their role or group composition. Such uniformity suggests these aspects are critical pain points for understanding and improving the approach to PT.

Misalignment in the rules of engagement or scope definition, such as unclear objectives, insufficient communication, or lack of agreement on the testing boundaries, further exacerbated these problems, resulting in misunderstandings between the testing team and the organization. Based on the experience of the participants, these issues often lead to reports that either overlook critical vulnerabilities or focus on less relevant areas, ultimately diminishing the effectiveness of the penetration test.

Defining the methodology has been shown to be a very important part of the penetration test. Without such a structured approach, testing can become inconsistent, with gaps in coverage that leave critical vulnerabilities undiscovered.

“The methodology part, how it is done, this should be the first thing. . .”

“If there is no methodology and there is just that you have this XML vulnerability like here in the demo, this is. It might not be enough.”

C. FINDING

A notable finding mentioned in every focus group was the strong need to include positive findings. Participants across all groups emphasized the importance of balancing critical feedback with positive aspects to ensure a more constructive and motivating approach. This widespread recognition underscores the value of highlighting successes alongside areas for improvement.

Another finding, while not mentioned in all focus groups, but deeply discussed within one particular group, is the need for reproducibility. A participant defined reproducibility as a key aspect:

“ability to understand and then reproduce the issue without having to bring in the pen tester.”

Reproducibility can be achieved through the provision of a Proof of Concept.

“The first thing from developer side is that I would like to reproduce this as possible. And check by myself, it’s really so important, so vulnerable?”

And then of course, to fix it. But you already see the report, you’re already providing. You have to, I mean, you’re providing already payloads, what payloads you use, what data you receive. And then this is already a good explanation that what kind of risk, what kind of data you can get from this penetration method.”

The participants identified possible improvements that could be made in report writing, adding the CVSS score to each finding. However, there is an opposite perception on the subject. A few participants mentioned the lack of usability of the CVSS scoring system. Implementing a more usable scoring system that would clearly communicate the severity and urgency of each vulnerability could help organizations prioritize their response efforts more effectively.

Providing a detailed description of how each vulnerability was discovered, including the tools and techniques used, would add to the valuable context of the professional trying to reproduce the vulnerability that not only validates the finding but also guides the organization in understanding the root causes and potential exploitation paths.

The discussion of a clearer description highlighted that the report is not just a list of issues, but a comprehensive guide to improving security posture.

D. RECOMMENDATION

More technical roles often mentioned the need for clearer descriptions in order to make them more actionable and understandable. An important aspect is to avoid copy-pasted recommendations that are often generic and do not address the specific context of the organization. Instead, expected recommendations are tailored to the particular vulnerabilities found, providing specific and relevant advice on remediation for both technical and non-technical individuals.

“I think that could create another problem for my managerial roles that are not that tech savvy because they want that. I think this was just a snippet of the overall report that I think perhaps there should be some sort of disclaimer or more broader sentences are clear about the overall risk management or what to do with this sort of report.”

However, it is necessary to be very careful with highly specific recommendations. While these recommendations should be tailored to the environment, the recipients of the report should not expect the provided solution to be immediately usable without proper adaptation and testing within their specific context. Otherwise, this may result in an insufficiently addressed vulnerability. Professionals may be inclined to use the provided advice as-is. This already happens, for example, with Android code snippets from Stack Overflow [20].

We see the part of the recommendation of the finding in the PT report as our main area of interest for future research, as based on the study results, the part that impacts the security process happening while mitigating the vulnerabilities found.

We plan to experiment with providing multiple mitigation options, preferred mitigation or even adding the possible impact of suggested mitigation in our future work.

E. CUSTOMIZATION

Machine readability in PT reports refers to the format and structure of these documents being optimized for automated processing by software tools, rather than being exclusively human-readable, as they are typically provided. Reports in standardized formats, such as JSON, XML, or CSV, with clearly defined schemas, could improve efficiency.

“Actually, the main problem is how to import these findings into our workflow management system. And if we get only the PDF file, then it’s problematic. Because then there is a lot of hand work.”

F. POSITIVE TALK

At the focus groups, the participants discussed that the recommendation for mitigation of vulnerability is often generic or not tailored to the specific needs of the customer. The participants also discussed whether the penetration tester should really be the one providing the mitigation or only providing the information about the existence of the vulnerability. However, the resulting opinion was positive, claiming that the recommendation given by the penetration tester helps, even when it might not define the exact steps that will be performed in reality.

G. TARGET GROUPS

Participant feedback suggested labeling the proposed mitigation, with labels suggesting the role typically responsible for the mitigation. For example, for an issue in the development part, use the label “dev”; for a configuration problem, use the label “config”. Using straightforward language, well-organized sections, and consistent terminology could, based on user feedback, make reports more accessible to both technical and non-technical stakeholders.

H. ADVANCED CHALLENGES

We do not consider the theme of advanced challenges as the direction of our future interest. However, the theme has been widely discussed. Ensuring consistency across all types of security testing, such as PT, vulnerability assessments, third-party component analysis, or static analysis, requires standardizing methodologies, tools, and reporting formats.

If the methodologies for various security tests were aligned, it could enable comprehensive risk coverage, seamless integration of findings, and efficient remediation through centralized dashboards and unified risk metrics.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The usability of PT reports is a topic that has received limited attention, despite its critical role in improving organizational security. To address this gap, we conducted a three user workshop studies with the consumers of PT

reports using two distinct methods: surveys and focus groups. Our research aimed to explore whether PT reports meet usability expectations and to identify areas for enhancement. From our analysis, we categorized the findings into three key categories: gaps in the current usability of the reports, potential improvements to bridge these gaps, and the insights of report consumers.

The study revealed that significant usability challenges persist. We identified eight themes that contain 29 findings. The themes are divided into themes: PT finding, recommendation, crucial parts, approach to PT, customization, advanced challenges, target groups, and positive talk.

The results of this study emphasize key findings across all themes. The study revealed which parts of the reports are the most crucial for specific target groups. This emphasized the importance of aligning the report content with each target audience.

Key outcomes of the study with respect to approach to PT include gaps in properly defining scope, rules of engagement, and methodology before the PT. The results also show an inadequate description of the finding in the PT report and the importance of adding positive findings to the PT report. Furthermore, our research addresses security advice within the recommendation of each finding in the report, such as copy-pasted generic mitigations, having multiple options of mitigation, declaring an impact of proposed mitigations, and defining preferred mitigation if multiple of them are proposed.

These results provide a foundation for further studies with the aim of enhancing the usability of PT reports, offering practical recommendations to improve both their clarity and impact. By addressing identified gaps and integrating user feedback, organizations can make their PT reports more actionable, thus improving the overall security posture. Future work will involve developing and testing prototypes of improved report formats, assessing their impact, and further exploring how to align PT reports with the needs of diverse target groups.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was carried out as part of the Project Cyber-Security Excellence Hub in Estonia and South Moravia (CHESS). The authors thank the companies AEC and Cybernetica for their collaboration and the opportunity to gather feedback from their customers, consumers of penetration testing reports. ChatGPT was used to polish some sentences.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. M. Z. A. Shebli and B. D. Beheshti, “A study on penetration testing process and tools,” in *Proc. IEEE Long Island Syst., Appl. Technol. Conf. (LISAT)*, May 2018, pp. 1–7.
- [2] A. G. Bacudio, X. Yuan, B. T. B. Chu, and M. M. Jones, “An overview of penetration testing,” *Int. J. Netw. Secur. Appl.*, vol. 3, no. 6, pp. 19–38, Nov. 2011.
- [3] “Guide to secure Web services,” Dept. U.S. Dept. of Commerce, Washington, National Institute of Standards and Technology, Washington, DC, USA, Tech. Rep. 800-95, 2007.

- [4] S. Manfredi, M. Ceccato, G. Sciarretta, and S. Ranise, "Do security reports meet usability?: Lessons learned from using actionable mitigations for patching TLS misconfigurations," in *Proc. 16th Int. Conf. Availability, Rel. Secur.*, Aug. 2021, pp. 1–13.
- [5] Y. Acar, M. Backes, S. Fahl, D. Kim, M. L. Mazurek, and C. Stransky, "You get where you're looking for: The impact of information sources on code security," in *Proc. IEEE Symp. Secur. Privacy (SP)*, May 2016, pp. 289–305.
- [6] M. N. Zakaria, P. A. Phin, N. Mohamad, S. A. Ismail, M. N. Kama, and O. Yusop, "A review of standardization for penetration testing reports and documents," in *Proc. 6th Int. Conf. Res. Innov. Inf. Syst. (ICRIIS)*, Dec. 2019, pp. 1–5.
- [7] A. P. Felt, A. Ainslie, R. W. Reeder, S. Consolvo, S. Thyagaraja, A. Bettes, H. Harris, and J. Grimes, "Improving SSL warnings: Comprehension and adherence," in *Proc. 33rd Annu. ACM Conf. Hum. Factors Comput. Syst.*, New York, NY, USA, Apr. 2015, pp. 2893–2902.
- [8] K. Krombholz, W. Mayer, M. Schmiedecker, and E. Weippl, "I have no idea what I'm doing'-on the usability of deploying HTTPS," in *Proc. 26th USENIX Secur. Symp.*, Vancouver, BC, Canada, Aug. 2017, pp. 1339–1356.
- [9] J. M. Haney, M. Theofanos, Y. Acar, and S. S. Prettyman, "We make it a big deal in the company': Security mindsets in organizations that develop cryptographic products," in *14th Symp. Usable Privacy Secur. (SOUPS)*, Baltimore, MD, USA, Aug. 2018, pp. 357–373.
- [10] C. Bellman and P. C. van Oorschot, "Systematic analysis and comparison of security advice as datasets," *Comput. Secur.*, vol. 124, Jan. 2023, Art. no. 102989.
- [11] M. Nachtigall, M. Schlichtig, and E. Bodden, "A large-scale study of usability criteria addressed by static analysis tools," in *Proc. 31st ACM SIGSOFT Int. Symp. Softw. Test. Anal.*, Jul. 2022, pp. 532–543.
- [12] D. Barrera, C. Bellman, and P. C. van Oorschot, "A close look at a systematic method for analyzing sets of security advice," *J. Cybersecurity*, vol. 9, no. 1, Jan. 2023, Art. no. tyad013.
- [13] J. Smith, B. Johnson, E. Murphy-Hill, B. Chu, and H. R. Lipford, "Questions developers ask while diagnosing potential security vulnerabilities with static analysis," in *Proc. 10th Joint Meeting Found. Softw. Eng.*, NY, NY, USA, Aug. 2015, pp. 248–259.
- [14] Y. Acar, C. Stransky, D. Wermke, C. Weir, M. L. Mazurek, and S. Fahl, "Developers need support, too: A survey of security advice for software developers," in *Proc. IEEE Cybersecurity Develop. (SecDev)*, Sep. 2017, pp. 22–26.
- [15] J. Zhang, S. Liu, X. Wang, T. Li, and Y. Liu, "Learning to locate and describe vulnerabilities," in *Proc. 38th IEEE/ACM Int. Conf. Automated Softw. Eng. (ASE)*, Sep. 2023, pp. 332–344.
- [16] D. Lazar, H. Chen, X. Wang, and N. Zeldovich, "Why does cryptographic software fail?: A case study and open problems," in *Proc. 5th Asia-Pacific Workshop Syst.*, New York, NY, USA, Jun. 2014, pp. 1–7.
- [17] A. Majumdar, "Thematic analysis in qualitative research," *J. Agricult. Sci.*, vol. 18, pp. 604–622, Oct. 2021.
- [18] S. Klivan, S. Höltervenhoff, R. Pankus, K. Markey, and S. Fahl, "Everyone for themselves? A qualitative study about individual security setups of open source software contributors," in *Proc. IEEE Symp. Secur. Privacy (SP)*, Los Alamitos, CA, USA, May 2024, pp. 1065–1082.
- [19] N. McDonald, S. Schoenebeck, and A. Forte, "Reliability and inter-rater reliability in qualitative research: Norms and guidelines for CSCW and HCI practice," *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.*, vol. 3, no. CSCW, pp. 1–23, Nov. 2019.
- [20] F. Fischer, K. Bottinger, H. Xiao, C. Stransky, Y. Acar, M. Backes, and S. Fahl, "Stack overflow considered harmful? The impact of copy&paste on Android application security," in *Proc. IEEE Symp. Secur. Privacy (SP)*, May 2017, pp. 121–136.

AGATA KRUIKOWA received the degree and Ph.D. degrees in social informatics and computer science from Masaryk University, Czech Republic. She was a member with the Centre for Research on Cryptography and Security, Masaryk University. She currently works in defensive security. Her research interests include authentication for both end users and IT professionals in the field of usable security, often in collaboration with commercial companies.

MARIA PIBILOTA MURUMAA received the bachelor's degree in computer science from the University of Tartu, and the joint master's degree in cybersecurity from the University of Tartu and Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia. She is currently a Cybersecurity Engineer with a focus on penetration testing and has previous experience developing security sensitive systems.

VÁCLAV (VASHEK) MATYÁŠ received the Ph.D. degree from Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic. He is currently a Professor with Masaryk University and heading its Centre for Research on Cryptography and Security. He is a member with the Research, Development and Innovation Council of the Government of Czech Republic. He worked in the past with Red Hat Czech, CyLab, Carnegie Mellon University, as a Fulbright-Masaryk Visiting Scholar with the Center for Research on Computation and Society, Harvard University, Microsoft Research Cambridge, University College Dublin, and Ubilab, UBS AG, and a Royal Society Postdoctoral Fellow with the Cambridge University Computer Laboratory. He also worked on the Common Criteria and in ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27. His research interests include applied cryptography and security and has published well over 200 peer-reviewed papers and articles and has co-authored several books. Can be contacted at matyas AT fi.muni.cz.

KATARINA GALANSKA received the dual degree in IT security from the Faculty of Information Technology, Brno University of Technology, and the University of South Wales, Cardiff. She is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree with the Centre for Research on Cryptography and Security, Masaryk University. She worked in offensive cybersecurity, for the past several years. Her research interests include penetration testing reports concerning IT professionals in the field of usable security, in collaboration with commercial companies.

MIKE JUST received the M.C.S. and Ph.D. degrees in cryptography and computer security from Carleton University, Ottawa, ON, Canada. He is currently an Associate Professor with Heriot-Watt University, Edinburgh, U.K. He applies human-computer interaction and machine learning techniques to solve computer security and digital forensics problems. You can find more information at <http://www.justmikejust.wordpress.com/>.

...